

Supplementary Figure S2. Complementation growth curves of $\Delta aceE$ and $\Delta aceF$ in M9 0.5% glucose media. $\Delta aceE$ and $\Delta aceF$ strains were complemented with IPTG-inducible vector pMB66EH. WT and $\Delta aceE$ strains were induced with 1mM IPTG whereas $\Delta aceF$ was induced with 0.01mM IPTG. (+) indicates the addition of IPTG inducer whereas (-) indicates the lack thereof. 'pe' denotes an empty vector control whereas 'pE' and 'pF' indicate the complementation plasmid contains the *aceE* and *aceF* open reading frames, respectively. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.